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Human presence is positively related to the number of birds calls and songs. Assessment in a national park --Manuscript Draft--

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Human presence is positively related to the number of bird calls and songs. Assessment in a national park

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Abstract

Human disturbance has been shown to provoke physiological and behavioral responses in birds, so nature-based tourism might reduce bird abundance and diversity. The negative consequences of human disturbance might be expected to be maximized during eventual massive events in highly protected areas such as national parks. In this study, the consequences for soundscapes of human presence and disturbance of thousands of visitors during an ornithological fair (massive event) on the bird community of the Monfragüe National Park (Spain) were analyzed. We found that the number and diversity of bird vocalizations did not decrease during the massive event. In contrast, the presence of people in the Monfragüe National Park was associated with an increase in the number and diversity of vocalizations. The effect of human presence on the number of calls and songs differed: the number of calls mainly increased during the massive event when people were present, while the number of songs increased when people were present, particularly during the measurement campaign without the massive event. The human shield hypothesis, along with other behavioral and environmental factors, might potentially explain the results obtained.

Keywords: bird vocalizations; nature-based tourism; habituation; human disturbance; human shield hypothesis

1. Introduction

Humans may be perceived by animals as predators (Frid and Dill 2002; Beale and Monaghan 2004; Meisingset et al. 2022). Human presence can have direct impacts on wildlife by altering behavior, physiology, and reproduction of animals (Stillman and Goss-Custard 2002; Williams et al. 2006; Sibbald et al. 2011; Knapp et al. 2013; Ohashi et al. 2013; French et al. 2017; van der Mescht et al. 2021). These effects can be observed in prey species, but also in common predators (Lovell et al. 2022), which, in turn, can determine the presence and activity of prey species.

Impacts of human presence have been studied in birds. Human disturbance can alter heart rates and stress hormone levels, or increase vigilance or flight (Fernández-Juricic and Tellería 2000; Weimerskirch et al. 2002; Beale and Monaghan 2004; Caro 2005; Stankowich and Blumstein 2005; Price 2008; Møller 2008, 2010, 2012; Blumstein 2014; Formenti et al. 2015). The consequences of human disturbance on birds' physiology and behavior might drive to a decrease in survival or reproduction, and the abandonment of the area (Anderson and Keith 1980; Arlettaz et al. 2005; Tarjuelo et al. 2015; Bötsch et al. 2017; Tablado and Jenni 2017). Accordingly, human disturbance has been shown to reduce bird density and species richness (van der Zande et al. 1947; Pfister et al. 1992; Kangas et al. 2010; Steven and Castley 2013; Arlettaz et al. 2015; Bötsch et al. 2017, 2018).

Nature-based tourism involves human disturbance and, therefore, has the potential to cause considerable effects on bird communities (Kerbiriou et al. 2009; Kangas et al. 2010; Steven and Castley 2013; Rösner et al. 2014; Bötsch et al. 2018). On the other hand, nature-based tourism can involve well-being of local people and favours conservation (Mayer 2014; Robalino and Villalobos 2015; Das and Hussain 2016;

1 Stronza et al. 2019). Research is necessary to ensure the sustainability of this human
2 activity, mainly in protected areas.
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4 National parks are widely known, highly protected areas around the world (Dudley
5 2008). In these areas, human activities which might be expected to affect nature
6 conservation should be considered and monitored. Impacts of tourism on wildlife
7 conservation in national parks have been found to be positive (conservation support of
8 local people, funds for conservation, increase the number of wild animals) or negative
9 (introduce invasive species, increase conflicts between human and wild animals; see
10 review in Rhama et al. 2020). In these protected areas, the relevance of human
11 disturbance on bird communities can be maximized during eventual touristic massive
12 events. Because of their special protection regimes, this type of events in national parks
13 are expected to be rare. When massive human events are conducted in national parks,
14 the impacts on wildlife deserve research.
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31 Monfragüe National Park is a Spanish protected area where tourism benefits local
32 communities (e.g., Sánchez et al. 2020). However, human presence might have negative
33 consequences on animal species such as birds. Additionally, a massive human event
34 occurs annually in Monfragüe National Park that might have a deep impact on wildlife:
35 the International Ornithological Tourism Fair (FIO according to its Spanish name).
36 During this event there is a significant increase in the number of people throughout the
37 park. In addition, the FIO fair is held in winter, when thermoregulatory energy demands
38 increase (Wiersma and Piersma 1994; Stillman and Goss-Custard 2002) and therefore
39 the impact on species such as birds is likely to be severe. In view of this, the aim of this
40 study was to analyze the consequences of human presence and the massive disturbance
41 of visitors during the FIO fair on the bird community in Monfragüe National Park.
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1 Birds might avoid the areas in Monfragüe National Park where human presence
2 increases. Additionally, the abandonment of the area by birds might be expected during
3 the FIO fair due to the massive presence of people. The impact of human disturbance on
4 bird communities can be evaluated by monitoring bird numbers and distribution through
5 transect or point count surveys conducted by human observers. The drawbacks of these
6 survey methods, such as observer biases or limited detectability of certain species, have
7 prompted the application of alternative techniques, including acoustic methods (Zwart
8 et al. 2014; Abrahams and Geary 2020). Therefore, the soundscape was the variable we
9 analyzed to infer the impact on bird community.
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21 Sound has been used for decades to survey birds and obtain population census
22 information (Ralph and Scott 1981; Robbins and van Welzen 1969) and is nowadays
23 recorded to monitor biodiversity trends (Sueur et al., 2019). However, in addition to the
24 study of animal sound (bioacoustics), there is growing interest in the relationship of
25 natural and anthropogenic sounds to the state of ecological systems with different levels
26 of protection and human presence (ecoacoustics; Sueur and Farina 2015, Xie et al.
27 2020). Therefore, ecoacoustics broadens the scope of acoustic research to include
28 bioacoustics and soundscape ecology. There are two aspects of sound included in
29 ecoacoustics that are related to ecosystem management: response indicator (estimating
30 the diversity of vocal organisms) and stress indicator (examining the effects of human
31 activity; Farina and Gage 2017). Both aspects are related to the objective of the present
32 study.
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50 Regarding the quantification of biodiversity from sound recordings, two
51 methodologies are commonly used. Listening to sound recordings for species
52 identification is one of them. Previous studies show a high correlation between bird
53 species identified by listening to recordings and in field observations (Haselmayer and
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Quinn 2000; Joo 2009). Nowadays there are also web applications based on artificial neural network for bird recognition (BirdNET). Bioacoustic indices are also used to measure biodiversity (Sueur et al. 2014; Zhao et al. 2019). These indices obtained from environmental recordings depend on the characteristics of the sounds in the recording, i.e. the diversity, complexity, degree of uniformity or spectral composition of the sounds (Farina and Gage 2017). Moreover, the number and richness of bird vocalizations have been used to determine the presence and abundance of bird species, mainly in forest areas (Chen and Maher 2006; Pérez-González et al. 2021). Therefore, we hypothesize that human presence and the FIO fair (massive event) reduce bioacoustic indices of biodiversity in Monfragüe National Park. We compared diversity measurements related to bird vocalizations in situations with low and high human disturbance.

Despite bird abundance and biodiversity can be quantified using sound recordings, it is important to consider the behavioral aspects of the bird soundscape. Birds utilize vocalizations (songs and calls) as communicative signals to transmit information (Catchpole and Slater 2008). Songs and calls differ in terms of complexity, length, and the context of vocalization. Songs are more complex and longer than calls. Both types of vocalizations also serve different functions and are motivated by distinct stimuli. While songs are typically associated with territorial defense, courtship, and mating, calls are generally linked to alarm functions and social cohesion (Catchpole and Slater 2008). Therefore, we predict that human presence might have different effects on each type of vocalization. In response to perceiving human presence as a risk, birds might choose to fly away (Frid and Dill 2002), resulting in a decrease in the frequency of songs. Alternatively, if birds choose to remain in the presence of humans, the frequency of defensive behaviors and alarm calls might increase (Knight and Temple 1986;

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Leavesley and Magrath 2005). In order to gain further insights into the effect of human presence on bird behavior, we also investigated whether human presence differentially affects the frequency of bird songs and calls.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Monfragüe National Park and International Ornithological Tourism Fair

The Monfragüe National Park is located in the Spanish region of Extremadura (39°49'12" N, 5°58'12" W). Monfragüe has 18,396 ha and it is considered one of the biggest and best preserved areas of Mediterranean forest in Europe. Within the national park there are patches of highly conserved forest and areas with different levels of human intervention such as *dehesas*. The Mediterranean forest is composed of cork and holm oak trees (*Quercus suber*, *Q. ilex*) and several scrub species such as strawberry tree (*Arbutus unedo*), laurustinus (*Viburnum tinus*), myrtle (*Mirtus communis*), false olive (*Phillyrea angustifolia*), heaths (*Erica* spp.), or rockroses (*Cystus* spp.). The *dehesas* are open grassland areas with scattered cork oaks and holm oaks. They were created by transforming the Mediterranean forest to favour livestock. In the park, there are two main rivers (Tajo and Tiétar) surrounded by quartzitic mountain ranges with large rocks and cliffs. These habitats are important natural refuges to the nesting of raptors, vultures, or storks. Most of these species can be easily observed from conditioned lookouts dispersed throughout the park. In addition to the flagship species that can be easily observed, the existence of an abundant and diverse bird community makes Monfragüe National Park an important area for bird conservation and the development of ornithological tourism in Europe. The estimated number of visitors was around 67,000 per year (Junta de Extremadura, 2019; data 2016-2019). Therefore, around 183 visitors per day can be estimated.

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Within Monfragüe National Park, managers offer three routes for visitors: green, red, and yellow (Figures 1 and S1). The three routes start in the only village within the national park, Villarreal de San Carlos (Figure S1). The green route (7.9 km) is a trail that connect the riparian forest of the Malvecino stream with the Gimio hill. The red route (16 Km) is a trail throughout the most conserved Mediterranean forest in the park. The yellow route (8.9 km) is a road throughout the Tajo and Tiétar rivers. Along the routes, there are several observation points and lookouts where people congregate to observe birds and to enjoy the landscape. The start point for all routes is Villarreal de San Carlos (Figure S1).

The consideration of Monfragüe as one of the most important areas to ornithological tourism in Europe is also due to the hold of the FIO fair. The last FIO fair that were carried out previously to the Spanish confinement for the COVID-19 pandemic (February 2020) received 16,900 visitors. Around 480 professional encounters took place and more than 55 companies related to ornithology attended to the event. More than 100 activities and conferences for visitors were conducted. During the FIO fair, the number of vehicles in the roads of Monfragüe increases significantly. Professional encounters and activities took place in Villarreal de San Carlos. However, most people use the attendance to the FIO fair to visit other areas, lookouts, or routes in the national park.

2.2. *Data collection*

Sampling points ($N = 18$) were located in the three routes of Monfragüe National Park (6 in the green route, 8 in red route, and 4 in the yellow route; Figure 1). Locations with sonorous and landscaped interest, as well as signposted lookouts were included as sampling points. The minimum distance between two sampling points was 90.5 meters. At these sampling points, a portable Zoom H6 recorder with Roland Binaural

1 microphones was used to record bird sounds for 5 minutes. Bird sounds were recorded
2 in two measurement campaigns: 15 days before the International Ornithological
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4 Tourism Fair (February 13th, 2020) and during the fair (February 28th, 2020). Therefore,
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6 data were collected in two conditions: “no event” (15 days before the FIO fair) and
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8 “event” (during the FIO fair). Both measurement campaigns began at the same time
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10 during the morning and the surveys along the sampling points were conducted in the
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12 same order (red route from the west to the east, green route from the south to the north
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14 and yellow route from the west to the east). Both measurement campaigns finished at
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16 similar time during the afternoon. We recorded the order of data collection at the
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18 sampling points within each route (*time* variable) to account for the potential effect of
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20 the time of day on our results. Weather conditions on the days of data collection were
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22 similar (temperature ranged between 14° C and 15 ° C, sun and clouds, wind speed ≤ 7
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24 km/h). For each sampling point we registered the presence of people in the area during
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26 data collection. Due to the importance of water on habitat features and the presence of
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28 wildlife in Mediterranean ecosystems (Olea et al. 2005), we registered whether there
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30 were water resources less than 50 meters apart from each sampling point. This distance
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32 was arbitrary, but variations of the value did not change the obtained results (not
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34 shown).

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43 The free software Sonic Visualiser (<https://www.sonicvisualiser.org/>) and Audacity
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45 (<https://www.audacityteam.org>) were used to perform the analyses and management of
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47 recordings. All the vocalizations (songs and calls, see below) in the recordings were
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49 analyzed in order to identify the bird species that emitted the sound. Species
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51 identification was conducted mainly aurally by the authors’ experience, although the
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53 process was supported by the visual inspection of spectrograms. We used the BirdNET
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55 web page (<https://birdnet.cornell.edu/>) to verify identifications and to manage doubts. A
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1 small proportion of calls could not be identified as belonging to a specific species (see
2 results). We used Birds of the World from The Cornell Lab of Ornithology
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4 (<https://birdsoftheworld.org>) as reference for scientific names.
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7 In those sampling points with high sound level proceeding from other environmental
8 sound sources (motors of vehicles, or people talking loudly), sounds were filtered out by
9 their frequencies to clearly identify bird vocalizations.
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13 Different types of vocalizations were identified in passerine birds. In these species,
14 vocalizations were categorized as calls or sounds. Songs were considered as complex
15 longer vocalizations for which the spectrogram shows different segments with different
16 frequencies. We referred calls as shorter and simpler vocalizations for which the
17 spectrogram shows a continuous segment or spot.
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27 From each recording, the number of recorded vocalizations produced by each bird
28 species was counted. Calls and short songs (less than 1 second) were counted as discrete
29 vocalizations. Longer songs were registered as a number of vocalizations equal to the
30 number of seconds that the song lasted (see Pérez-González et al. 2021). Unidentified
31 vocalizations were included as vocalizations of an additional species. The number of
32 vocalizations was used to obtain three diversity measures for each recording: species
33 richness (number of species that emitted at least one vocalizations), and the Shannon
34 and Simpson indices. These three measurements were used to assess the impact of the
35 massive event on the bioacoustic diversity in the National Park. Additionally, calls and
36 songs were analyzed separately to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the
37 potential effect of human presence on bird behavior.
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54 *2.3. Statistical analyses*

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1 We firstly assessed the effect of human presence on the general soundscape of the
2 Monfragüe National Park. The effects of the massive event and the presence of people
3 on acoustic diversity measures were assessed by conducting three models, each with a
4 different response variable: species richness (number of bird species), and the Shannon
5 and Simpson indices which take into account both the number of species and the
6 number of vocalizations per species. Note that these diversity measures estimate the
7 diversity of vocalizations rather than the biodiversity of species. Therefore, for each
8 sampling point, a single value was obtained for each of the three diversity measures. In
9 all three models, the measurement campaign (no event *vs.* event), the presence of people
10 (sampling point with and without people), and the interaction of both were included as a
11 fixed factor, and time within route and sampling point within route were incorporated as
12 nested random effects. Water resource (sampling point with or without water resources)
13 and route were initially included as fixed factors. However, the models were simplified
14 by conducting a background stepwise procedure in which the model with the lowest
15 AIC value was selected. Water resource and route did not appear in the simplified
16 models. For the species richness, we conducted a generalized linear mixed effect model
17 (GLMMs) fitted by maximum likelihood using the Poisson distribution. For the
18 Shannon and Simpson indices, linear mixed effect models (LMMs) fitted by maximum
19 likelihood were performed.

20 On the other hand, we categorized bird vocalizations into calls and songs to explore
21 further insights into the potential factors influencing the relationship between human
22 presence and the number of vocalizations. For that, the effects of the massive event and
23 the presence of people on the number of calls and songs were assessed by conducting
24 two GLMMs for zero-inflated count data fitted by maximum likelihood using the
25 Poisson distribution. The model was repeated separately for calls and songs. In both

1 models, the number of vocalizations (calls or songs) produced by each bird species was
2 included as the response variable. The fixed factors included in the models were people
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4 (sampling point with or without people), measurement campaign (no event vs. event),
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6 and the interaction of both. The bird species was considered as random factor, and time
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8 within route and sampling point within route were incorporated as nested random
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10 effects. Additionally, the water resource variable was incorporated into the model as a
11
12 fixed factor. As the interactions between people and measure campaign were significant
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14 in both models (with calls and songs as response variables; see results), we repeated the
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16 models by changing the reference for the measure campaign factor.
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21 Biodiversity measures were obtained with *vegan* package (Oksanen et al. 2020) in R
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23 software (R Core Team, 2019). LMMs were performed with *nlme* package (Pinheiro et
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25 al. 2020) in R software. GLMMs for the total number of vocalizations and the species
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27 richness were conducted with *lme4* package (Bates et al. 2015) in R software. GLMMs
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29 for zero-inflated count data with a single zero-inflation parameter applying to all
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31 observations were performed with *glmmTMB* package (Brooks et al., 2017) in R
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33 software. Predict effect plots conducted with *effects* package (Fox 2003) in R were used
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35 to observe the effect of the factors interaction on zero-inflated count data.
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41 **3. Results**

42 All recordings registered 4,375 bird vocalizations. The mean number of recorded
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44 vocalizations per minute was 24.306. We identified 33 bird species and 7.406% of the
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46 vocalizations were not identified. Table 1 shows the number of vocalizations for each
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48 bird species.
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52 We met people observing wildlife in 4 lookouts used as sampling points (2 in the red
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54 route and 2 in the yellow route). In all these lookouts, there were more than 5 people in
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56 both measurement campaigns. However, the number of observed people were very
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1 different between both measurement campaigns. We counted 5 and 8 people in the
2 lookouts of the red route and 5 and 6 people in the lookouts of the yellow route during
3 the measurement campaign of “no event”. However, we counted 37 and 41 people in the
4 lookouts of the red route, and 26 and 22 people in the lookouts of the yellow route
5 during the FIO fair. See Table S1 in supplementary material for additional information
6 that illustrates human disturbance in both measurement campaigns. For all three
7 measures (species richness, and the Shannon and Simpson indices), the values of
8 acoustic biodiversity were higher during the massive event compared to the
9 measurement campaign with no event (Table 2, Figure 2). The measurement campaign
10 (“no event” vs. “event”) was the only factor that reached statistical significance for these
11 measures of acoustic biodiversity.
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26 After categorizing vocalizations into calls and songs, the number of vocalizations
27 varied depending on the measurement campaign and the presence of people in the
28 sampling point (Table 3, Figure 3). Furthermore, the interaction between both fixed
29 factors had a significant effect in both models, but this effect differed for calls and songs
30 (Table 3, Figure 3). The number of calls was higher during the massive event,
31 particularly when people were present in the sampling point (Table 3A and right panel
32 in Figure 3A). When “no event” was employed as the reference for the Event factor, the
33 effect of People did not reach statistical significance (Estimate = 0.596, Standard error =
34 0.433, $z = 1.377$, $p = 0.168$; left panel in Figure 3A). The number of songs was also
35 higher during the massive event, regardless of the presence of people. However, we also
36 recorded a high number of songs during the measurement campaign of “no event” when
37 people were present (Table 3B and left panel in Figure 3B). When “event” was used as
38 reference for the Event factor, the effect of People did not reach significance (Estimate
39 = 0.601, Standard error = 0.604, $z = 0.995$, $p = 0.320$; right panel in Figure 3B). The
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1 water resource factor was also positively related to both the number of calls and the
2 number of songs (Table 3).
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5 **4. Discussion**

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8 Bird soundscape was analyzed in two very different situations regarding human
9 disturbance. During the measurement campaign of “no event” there were few people in
10 the national park. The highest number of people we met in this day was 20 (see Table
11 S1). However, during the FIO fair there more than a thousand people in the national
12 park. Most of them were in Villarreal de San Carlos, but there were people throughout
13 the park. The number of people in the lookouts were not very different between
14 measurement campaigns due to their limited space, which prevented the gathering of a
15 large number of people. However, human presence and human activities differed
16 between both measurement campaigns.
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30 Human disturbance was expected to reduce the presence of birds in Monfragüe
31 National Park, at least in popular lookouts or during events with high people influx
32 (Rösner et al. 2014; Coppes et al. 2017; Bötsch et al. 2017, 2018). However, we did not
33 find a negative relationship between the presence of people and the bioacoustic indices
34 of biodiversity. Contrarily, the diversity of bird vocalizations increased during the
35 International Ornithological Tourism Fair. Furthermore, the number of calls and songs
36 were positively related to the human presence. These results can have important
37 implications on bird conservation in protected areas where touristic activities are
38 implemented.
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51 Non-assessed variables might induce a spurious relationship between human
52 presence and bioacoustic indices. For instance, high habitat quality in lookouts might be
53 responsible of the positive association between human presence and bioacoustic indices
54 of biodiversity. Accordingly, we found a positive effect of the existence of water
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1 resources on the number of calls and songs. Food availability or the presence of refuges
2 might also impact the spatial distribution of bird vocalizations. However, differences in
3
4 habitat quality do not explain why the frequency of bird vocalizations were higher
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6 during the massive event. The significant associations observed in both the spatial
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8 (People term in Table 3) and temporal (Event term in Tables 2 and 3) dimensions of
9
10 human presence in our study support the notion that the relationship between human
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12 presence and the number and diversity of vocalizations might not be spurious.
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17 On the other hand, the massive event occurred two weeks later than the measurement
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19 campaign of “no event”. This temporal delay makes the FIO fair closer to the
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21 reproductive period of Iberian birds and more frequent vocalizations related to mating
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23 might be expected. Songs are mainly associated with mating behaviors, while calls
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25 serve various functions (contact, alarm, mating; Catchpole and Slater 2008), so a
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27 prediction of this possible explanation would be that the increase in the number of
28
29 vocalizations during the massive event is primarily driven by a higher number of songs.
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31 Accordingly, the intensity of the measurement campaign effect was greater for songs
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33 compared to calls (Table 3 and Figure 3). However, the higher number of songs in the
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35 presence of people, particularly during the measurement campaign of “no event”,
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37 suggests that the temporal delay was not the sole variable associated with the increase in
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39 the number of vocalizations.
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46 The decrease in bird presence and vocalizations, as a means to avoid detection, was
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48 expected since birds can perceive humans as potential predators (Frid and Dill 2002;
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50 Beale and Monaghan 2004). The absence of a negative effect of human presence on the
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52 number and diversity of bird vocalizations may be attributed to a habituation process
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54 taking place in the bird community of Monfragüe National Park (see e.g. Villanueva et
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56 al. 2012). The intense reiterative benign interactions with humans can induce bird
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1 habituation (Fowler 1999; Webb and Blumstein 2005; Blumstein 2014). This type of
2 interactions is frequent in cities where birds show high levels of habituation to humans
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4 (Møller 2012; Blumstein 2014; Vincze et al. 2016).
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7 Habituation can explain why human presence does not seem to have a negative
8 impact on bird community. However, why do the number and diversity of vocalizations
9 increase in the presence of people? Firstly, we assume that the increase in the number of
10 vocalizations should not be due to an increase of bird abundance or biodiversity.
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12 Contrarily, it might be attributed to behavioral changes resulting from factors associated
13 with human presence. The following possible explanations are based on this
14 assumption.
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17 As a possible explanation, human activities might produce environmental
18 background noise and, as a consequence, birds might emit higher sound levels favoring
19 sound transmission and the detection from higher distances (Brumm 2004; Brumm and
20 Slabbekoorn 2005). Alternatively, humans might increase resource availability by food
21 provisioning (consciously or unconsciously) and, hence, increase interactions between
22 birds or change bird distribution and abundance (Knight 2009; Geffroy et al. 2015).
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25 Moreover, the higher number of vocalizations might also be explained by the increase in
26 the emitting of alarm calls in presence of people (Frid and Dill 2002; Catchpole and
27 Slater 2008). According to these possible explanations, we found a higher frequency of
28 calls mainly during the massive event in sampling points with presence of people, when
29 high human presence might motivate birds to communicate diverse information
30 (contact, alarm, mating).
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33 Finally, the reiterative benign interactions with humans might induce a phenomenon
34 previously detected in urban environments: the human shield (Valcarcel and Fernández-
35 Juricic 2009; Møller 2012; Geffroy et al. 2015). The human shield hypothesis explains
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1 the increase of the abundance of certain bird species in cities because a decrease of
2 native predators. Therefore, the human presence may create a safe situation that prevent
3 predation to birds. In Monfragüe National Park, the recorded vocalizations were mostly
4 emitted by bird species that can be predated by raptors such as sparrowhawk (*Accipiter*
5 *nisus*), peregrine falcon (*Falco peregrinus*), kites (*Milvus* spp.), goshawk (*Accipiter*
6 *gentilis*), or booted eagle (*Hieraaetus pennatus*) (Mañosa 1994; García et al. 1998;
7 Rizolli et al. 2005; García-Dios 2006; Hernández 2018). The presence of people in
8 Monfragüe National Park might act as a human shield that decreases the risk of being
9 attacked by a predator. The decrease in the predation risk can favor the emission of bird
10 vocalizations to transmit information (Catchpole and Slater 2008). But also, the
11 abundance and diversity of the bird community might increase in those areas with
12 human presence that act as attractive safe zones (Valcarcel and Fernández-Juricic 2009).
13 According to the human shield hypothesis, the frequency of songs maximized when
14 people were present during both measurement campaigns. Despite the human shield
15 hypothesis can explain the obtained results, we cannot rule out other explanations and
16 probably the outputs were due to the combination of several factors and processes.

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39 In summary, we found that the number and diversity of vocalizations increased in the
40 presence of people. Therefore, we might conclude that the human impact was positive
41 on the bird community of Monfragüe National Park. However, according to our
42 sampling procedure, we were unable to provide evidence of negative impacts of human
43 presence on the bird community. These impacts might be related to increase energetic
44 demand, food provisioning, reduced reaction to predators, or negative effect on predator
45 populations (Orams 2002; Carrascal et al. 2012; Geffroy et al. 2015). Future studies
46 about the effect of human presence on the entire bird community, including raptors or
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1 rates of food provisioning, can help to design strategies to make compatible nature-
2 based tourism and conservation in highly visited national parks.
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23 **Author's contributions**

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25
26 Javier Pérez-González: methodology, validation, formal analysis, investigation, data
27 curation, writing - original draft, writing - review & editing, visualization, supervision.
28
29 Guillermo Rey-Gozaló: validation, formal analysis, resources, data curation, writing -
30 review & editing, visualization, supervision, project administration, funding acquisition.
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32 Sebastián J. Hidalgo de Trucios: validation, investigation, writing - review & editing,
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57 **Declaration of competing interest**

1 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or
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7 **Data availability**

8 The data have been included as electronic supplementary material.
9

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Table 1. Total number of vocalizations and number of vocalizations per minute for each bird species in all the recordings.

Species	# Vocaliz. / per min	Species	# Vocaliz. / per min
<i>Fringilla coelebs</i>	954 / 5.30	<i>Curruca iberiae</i>	22 / 0.12
<i>Aegithalos caudatus</i>	513 / 2.85	<i>Prunella modularis</i>	20 / 0.11
<i>Cyanistes caeruleus</i>	433 / 2.41	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	20 / 0.11
<i>Serinus serinus</i>	350 / 1.94	<i>Cyanopica cooki</i>	19 / 0.11
<i>Erithacus rubecula</i>	317 / 1.76	<i>Phylloscopus collybita</i>	12 / 0.07
<i>Turdus merula</i>	282 / 1.57	<i>Sylvia atricapilla</i>	12 / 0.10
<i>Delichon urbicum</i>	219 / 1.22	<i>Periparus ater</i>	9 / 0.05
<i>Certhia brachydactyla</i>	198 / 1.10	<i>Spinus spinus</i>	5 / 0.03
<i>Parus major</i>	107 / 0.59	<i>Pyrrhula pyrrhula</i>	4 / 0.02
<i>Alectoris rufa</i>	104 / 0.58	<i>Cettia cetti</i>	3 / 0.02
<i>Lophophanes cristatus</i>	92 / 0.51	<i>Monticola solitarius</i>	3 / 0.02
<i>Columba spp.</i>	86 / 0.48	<i>Motacilla spp.</i>	3 / 0.02
<i>Linaria cannabina</i>	71 / 0.39	<i>Lanius meridionalis</i>	2 / 0.01
<i>Lullula arborea</i>	64 / 0.36	<i>Corvus corax</i>	1 / 0.01
<i>Troglodytes troglodytes</i>	58 / 0.32	<i>Galerida cristata</i>	1 / 0.01
<i>Sitta europaea</i>	40 / 0.22	<i>Curruca undata</i>	1 / 0.01
<i>Chloris chloris</i>	26 / 0.14	<i>Unidentified</i>	324 / 1.80

Table 2. Effect of measurement campaigns (Event) and the presence of people on acoustic biodiversity measures. A) Results from the GLMM with species richness as the dependent variable. B) Results from the LMM with the Shannon index as the dependent variable. C) Results from the LMM with the Simpson index as the dependent variable. In all three models, “No event” was used as reference for Event factor, sampling points without people as reference for People factor, and time within route and sampling point within route were incorporated as nested random effects. SE: standard error. *z*: statistic for GLMM with Poisson distribution (A). *t*: statistic for LMM (B and C). The degrees of freedom for the LMMs (B and C) were 16 (number of vocalizations and interaction of fixed factors) and 14 (presence of people). See Table S2 for the results of random effects.

	Term	Estimate	SE	<i>z/t</i>	<i>p</i>
A)	Intercept	1.209	0.148	8.176	<0.001
Species richness	Event	0.544	0.183	2.969	0.003
	People	0.347	0.270	1.267	0.205
	Event*People	-0.121	0.347	-0.350	0.727
B)	Intercept	0.684	0.129	5.313	<0.001
Shannon index	Event	0.503	0.182	2.765	0.014
	People	0.267	0.273	0.979	0.344
	Event*People	-0.318	0.386	-0.823	0.422
C)	Intercept	0.362	0.061	5.952	<0.001
Simpson index	Event	0.251	0.086	2.918	0.010
	People	0.131	0.129	1.015	0.327
	Event*People	-0.211	0.183	-0.156	0.265

Table 3. Effect of measurement campaigns (Event) and the presence of people on the number of calls (A) and songs (B). Table shows the results of the GLMM model after removing different non-significant terms and selecting the model with lowest AIC. The table shows the results for the combination of references in the fixed factors for which the effects were significant. Therefore, in the model for the number of calls (A), “event” was used as reference (R) for Event factor; in the model for the number of songs (B), “no event” was used as reference (R) for Event factor; in both models, sampling points without people were used as reference for People factor and sampling point with no water was used as reference for Water resource fixed factor. SE: standard error.

	Term	Estimate	SE	Z	p
A)	Intercept	0.373	0.426	0.876	0.381
Number of calls	Event (R: “event”)	-0.205	0.057	-3.616	<0.001
	People	0.723	0.218	3.319	<0.001
	Event*People	-0.525	0.100	-5.272	<0.001
	Water	1.784	0.240	7.419	<0.001
B)	Intercept	-0.014	0.460	-0.030	0.976
Number of songs	Event (R: “no event”)	1.832	0.129	14.162	<0.001
	People	1.997	0.198	10.105	<0.001
	Event*People	-1.444	0.166	-8.703	<0.001
	Water	0.927	0.171	5.426	<0.001

Fig. 1. Sampling points in Monfragüe National Park (Google Earth). Figure shows the sampling points in the red route (A), in the yellow route (B) and in the green route (C). Routes are drawn with coloured lines. The colour of the points represents the mean of the total number of vocalizations for both measurement campaigns. See also Figure S1. The UTM coordinates of some of the sampling points are as follows: Point 1: 29 S, 753751 m E, 4413075 m N; Point 2: 29 S, 755892 m E, 4415116 m N; Point 3: 29S, 753269 m E, 4415410 m N

1
2 **Fig. 2.** Acoustic biodiversity measures for both measurement campaigns (“no event” vs.
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4 “event”) and the people presence (sampling point without and with people). A), B), and
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6 C) graphs show results for each diversity measures. See Table 2.
7
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Fig. 2. Cont

B)

C)

Fig. 3. Effect of the interaction between measurement campaign (event vs. no event) and the presence of people on the number of calls (A) and songs (B). The figure shows predicted values and 95% confidence limits.

A)

Fig. 3. Cont.

B)

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